

Corrigendum

Cite this article: Sokolickova Z, Meyer A, and Vlachov AV. Changing Svalbard: Tracing interrelated socio-economic and environmental change in remote Arctic settlements – CORRIGENDUM. *Polar Record* 58(e43): 1. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0032247423000037>

Keywords:

Svalbard; Socio-economic change; Environmental change; Longyearbyen; Barentsburg; corrigendum

Changing Svalbard: Tracing interrelated socio-economic and environmental change in remote Arctic settlements – CORRIGENDUM

Zdenka Sokolickova, Alexandra Meyer and Andrian Viktorovich Vlachov

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0032247422000213>, Published by Cambridge University Press, 10 August 2022.

The authors apologise for the omission of funding declarations from the originally published version of this article. The missing information is given here:

Zdenka Sokolíčková's research was financed through the project CZ.02.2.69/0.0/0.0/18_070/00094 76 (bo)REALIFE: Overheating in the high Arctic: Qualitative anthropological analysis funded by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic and University of Hradec Králové. Alexandra Meyer's research for this article has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773421. The work of Andrian Vlachov is an output of a research project implemented as part of the Basic Research Program at HSE University.

Reference

Sokolickova, Z., Meyer, A., & Vlachov, A. V. (2022). Changing Svalbard: Tracing interrelated socio-economic and environmental change in remote Arctic settlements. *Polar Record*. Published by Cambridge University Press, 10 August 2022. doi: [10.1017/S0032247422000213](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0032247422000213).

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